

book reviews

edited by Susan Gannon

The Second Kind of Criticism

by Perry Nodelman

Peter Hunt. *Criticism, Theory, & Children's Literature*. Cambridge, MA and Oxford, England: Basil Blackwell, 1991.

The literary criticism I learn from comes in two kinds. The first kind persuades me to think as it does; the second kind leads me to think for myself.

The first kind is merely breathtaking—innovative, surprising, yet so persuasive that I have no choice but to approach all the texts I come across after reading it in the new terms it's provided me with. At this point in my inflexible middle age, this paradigm-shifting kind of experience doesn't happen very often; and indeed, I'm not sure I'd like to have my mind blown so explosively much more frequently than once or twice a decade—it's liberating, but it hurts. So I'm grateful for the second kind of criticism.

The second kind is less breathtaking than productively infuriating. It persuades me of the importance of the questions it raises, but not necessarily of the soundness of the answers it provides—and so I'm forced into an extensive dialogue with it, as I look for answers that will satisfy me more.

Peter Hunt's ambitious attempt to, as he says, use "critical theory and practice to help readers to deal with children's literature, and children's literature to help readers to deal with literary theory" (5) is criticism of the second kind. What follows is a report of my dialogue with it.

Hunt examines a significant body of theory in order to explore how it might challenge commonly held assumptions about children and their reading, about literature in general, and about children's literature in particular. One such assumption is that literary texts have intrinsic value, that Shakespeare's writing is inherently better, truer, more beautiful, than Barbara Cartland's or Beatrix Potter's—an assumption that leads people to downgrade children's literature in relation to adult masterpieces, and, within children's literature, to belittle those texts that children often do enjoy most. Hunt's perceptive analysis reveals the extent to which complacent statements about the supposedly eternal, universal value of great literature are actually culture-bound: ideological expressions of the interests of a particular group in a particular place and time.

Hunt also collapses the assumption that texts communicate the same meanings to all readers, so that the themes adult readers find in literary texts are the messages those texts do actually convey to children. He marshals a body of theory, both literary and psychological, to establish that there is "a considerable difference between what a child might perceive a text to be and what an adult decides it must be" (96). The central thrust of Hunt's argument here, and of his book as a whole, is to encourage us to partake in what he calls "childist criticism": doing our best to bypass the practices and

conclusions that conventional assumptions about both literature and childhood suggest to us, and "reading, as far as possible, from a child's point of view, taking into account personal, sub-cultural, experiential, and psychological differences between children and adults—in short, allowing the reader precedence over the book" (198).

It's obvious that the questions Hunt raises—what makes for value in children's literature and what we need to know about children's reading before we can determine it—are important ones. They are, I think, *the* important ones, the ones that ought to concern all of us who try to make sense of the phenomenon of children's literature. And Hunt's answers are good ones, both theoretically sound and eminently practical.

Nevertheless, I'm not satisfied by them. Although I want to accept them, I can't help noticing that there's a serious contradiction right at the heart of them.

Hunt's discussion of ideology includes a summary of an article by the theorist Terry Eagleton that reveals the contradiction. Eagleton argues, says Hunt, that "humans do not 'produce themselves.' They are produced by society, and in the process are given certain 'modes of subjectivity'; and the mode of subjectivity in our (western) society is one which deceives us into believing that we *do* produce ourselves" (146). Seen from the viewpoint of this sort of ideological theory, what we call a self or a personality is not some unique essence outside of and opposed to cultural forces—it is itself a construction of those cultural forces. In the case of our own society, those forces work paradoxically to persuade the subjects they construct that they are unique and self-controlled.

Hunt not only acknowledges that position, but even accepts it. Much of his discussion of ideology centers on the ways in which our culture constructs the subjectivity of its members, and he asserts that children's books are part of the process, that "what truly communicates in a text is the hidden attitude, the underlying philosophy and stance, the status accorded to books generally" (143) by their culture and that therefore, "when a child comes to choose [what to read], her or his capacity to choose will have been molded already by the ideologies of her or his mentors" (143).

But despite all this, he still insists that children are somehow free, that their selves are somehow not yet constructed, that they are somehow not yet enmeshed in ideology. And obviously, both can't be true.

If children are indeed free, then ideology isn't as powerful a force as Hunt wishes us to believe (which seems to me to be unlikely). But if ideology does indeed construct subjectivity, then no child more than a few days old isn't already enmeshed in cultural constraints and categories, already being "childlike" in ways ap-

proved and therefore expected and encouraged by its culture, already being programmed to read as children are expected to read.

Rather than confront this contradiction, Hunt studiously ignores it, carefully keeping the two contradictory ideas in separate parts of his book where they can't contaminate each other. When he's talking about ideology, he acknowledges that children are as enmeshed in it as is literature, as are adults. But when he's talking about children's reading, he conveniently forgets about the child as a subject of his culture's ideology and posits, instead, the child as unique self: an independent, innocent, spontaneous, imaginative free spirit, a being who triumphantly escapes all adult attempts at control, who remains at any point in his childhood as innocent of adult culture as a baby newly emerged from the womb.

The presence of an essentially non-ideological, essentially self-contained self at the heart of an argument that would seem to deny the possibility of her or his existence peculiarly confirms Hunt's conviction that it's impossible to say or do anything that doesn't have ideological content. This innocent extra-cultural child is clearly a manifestation of Hunt's own ideology, which triumphantly resists the pressure of the logic of the very ideas he purports to be espousing.

Hunt responds with some scorn to Eagleton's assertion that "the space of modern subjectivity is a prison camp which offers itself as an endless open horizon," and the myopic liberal-humanists patrol this camp, supporting the very oppression that their 'literature' purports to despise" (147). Hunt's scorn doesn't quite manage to conceal the fact that his own praise of "open texts"—those which he believes don't oppress young readers into controlled responses—requires him to posit a simplistic and limited image of what children are and of how they fit within the network of the culture they belong to. It also leads him to affirm as liberating a conception of self-producing and self-sufficient individuality of the sort that privileges the values of liberal, humanist, middle class intellectuals like himself (and, I blush to admit it, like me)—a conception that does, I am convinced, work to imprison children in the repressions and blindnesses of the contemporary Western middle-class culture that Hunt and I share. Hunt complains that Eagleton's analysis "suggests that all loving and caring teachers, doing their best to educate and to pass on the best and purest of values, are in fact a bunch of jackbooted fascists" (147); perhaps he needs to take a more careful look down at what he's got on his own feet.

In addition to their distinctive footwear, what allows us to identify even the most seemingly humanistic of fascists is their insistence on seeing individuals as nothing more than representatives of groups, their individual characters limited to the presumed characteristics of the groups in question. Hunt claims to believe in the existence and the sanctity of differences between individuals.

He claims that child readers are different from adult readers primarily because we are *all* different from each other and because we all read in the context of our differing experiences. But in fact, his central thesis—that we should do "childist" readings—depends centrally on a pair of assumptions that effectively deny the significance of those idiosyncratic differences: that all adults read alike, and that all children read alike.

Hunt makes generalizations about the "adult mind" and about adult modes of reading surprisingly often. And to prove his point that children respond differently from adults, he provides summaries of Piagetian theories of development that generalize children into easily identifiable stages—theories whose ideological content has been severely criticized not only by feminists but also by more

recent psychological researchers. He also insists that all children as a class belong to an "oral" culture, as such cultures have been defined by Walter Ong. This is to assume that those who cannot yet read form a culture separate from the literate culture surrounding and influencing them—a highly suspicious generalization, and one that works to erase the ways in which children in our society might be not only different from members of purely oral societies but also different from each other.

Nor is it only child and adult readers whose individual differences are being discounted under the surface of Hunt's public celebration of them. One of the central idiosyncrasies of this book about theory is Hunt's assertion that he has deliberately not named many of the theorists whose work he discusses. "The only point in mentioning a critic by name," he says, "is that the name acts as a shorthand reference to a group of ideas. Very few readers can actually make the necessary associations, and so the use of names frequently becomes either a weapon or a rather unhealthy totem-building activity" (10). Well, that *sounds* sane: what right-minded individual would want to indulge in an activity that's not only militaristic but bad for one's health? In fact, though, Hunt's refusal to name names is another way of ignoring significant differences, another way of bending the theories he discusses to make them fit into the invisible jackboots of his own liberal humanist mythology.

By presenting ideas actually associated with individual theorists as if they simply represented theory in general, Hunt manages to ignore any possibility of disputes *between* theorists, or indeed, in the area of literary theory as a whole. In doing so, he makes surprisingly seamless what is actually a field of differences, of intense and sometimes intensely confusing conflict.

Not surprisingly, no actual texts of theory appear in Hunt's "Selected Bibliography"; instead, he lists what he calls "Guides to Modern Criticism and Theory," books designed to make the hard ideas of structuralism or deconstruction available to more general audiences. The trouble with such books is exactly what makes them so useful in the first place: they distort theory in the very act of turning it into something more recognizable and more easily absorbed by readers like Hunt (and I again hasten to add, like myself) who were trained in more conventional, that is, more liberal and more humanist, modes of thinking. A proficient guide like Terry Eagleton has the ability to turn the craggy, difficult, disturbingly pun-filled writing of a Jacques Derrida into something clear, comprehensible, even comfortingly familiar—that is, everything that it is not. Hunt himself misrepresents theory just as these guides do: by divesting it of its alien strangeness, of the indeterminacies, contradictions, inconsistencies, and incompleteness that make it so disturbing and so exciting—by ignoring the individual differences of individual critics.

And yet—. As I suggested earlier, my main objection to this book is the degree to which Hunt insists so cheerfully on the sanctity of those individual differences, on the essential uniqueness of us all, a uniqueness that ideological theory makes extremely questionable. In other words, my objections to Hunt's book are as self-contradictory as the things I object to. It seems that I need to check out my own footwear.

And that suggests what my encounter with this book has forced me to think about—why I've found it so useful. It has taught me that if we're going to arrive at a more satisfying understanding of children's literature than we now have, then we're either going to have to eliminate, or else acknowledge and work with, exactly the

contradiction I've surfaced here, in both Hunt's thinking and my own: the paradoxical relationships of subjectivity and selfhood, ideology and personal experience.

In a sense, that's a dispute between theory and practice—between what our disinterested thinking tells us we logically ought to believe and what our acts of reading and being actually feel like to us. That Hunt's work and my response to it are marked by that conflict isn't surprising: it's at the heart of our encounter as literary specialists with children's literature.

On the one hand, we are scholars who, like all scholars, want merely to understand the phenomena we've chosen to learn about as completely as possible; but on the other, we almost always have some interest in what actual children actually do or might read, some additional agenda that relates to what and how we think real children really ought to be reading. Some of us use our literary expertise to recommend "good" literature for children—meaning, usually, that which celebrates liberal humanist values. Some, like Hunt, use it to privilege the indiscriminate and uncontrolled reading which *he* sees as liberating and humane and childlike. But we all find it hard to ignore the practical results for children of our theoretically objective studies.

And so, of course, our personal prejudices about those practical considerations contaminate our theoretical thinking. In Hunt's case, the contamination consists not only of the distortions that emerge from his liberal humanist faith in the uniqueness and self-governance of individuals, but also of a peculiar limitation in his view of what

children's literature is. He insists there's no point in including in it anything children no longer read because "the history of the children's book may be interesting to the adult, but not for the child" (62)—a statement which not only generalizes wildly about the historical interests of children but which also, presumably in the interests of practicality, closes off the sort of analysis of alternate versions of childhood that he might have been able to explore with more objectivity, and that therefore might well have enriched his understanding of how the books children *do* currently read work to construct highly specific forms of childhood subjectivity. His focus on practical benefits for children also causes him to forget his conviction that children *don't* read as adults intend when he favors open texts over closed ones; because if he's right and children *do* always read openly anyway, then why should we even worry about the attempts of closed texts to control them?

But again: and yet—. Ideological theory tells us that no supposedly objective analysis can be uncontaminated by personal prejudice. And the fact that Hunt's personal prejudices and practical concerns contaminate his book enough to force me to raise and explore these questions that relate so centrally to the contradiction inherent in the very existence of a children's literature produced and studied by adults suggests exactly why I think it's an important book—why it infuriated me, and why I strongly recommend it.

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Contextualizing the Personal Narrative

by Lots R. Kuznets

Stahl, Sandra Dolby. *Literary Folkloristics and the Personal Narrative*. Bloomington: Indiana UP, 1989.

Stahl's text was one of those fortunate finds that open library stacks provide. I don't remember what else I was looking for in the PN 900s but—intrigued enough by the "personal narrative" portion of the title to bring the book home—I later found myself impressed by Stahl's practice of "literary folkloristics." This discipline combines traditional folklore analysis with, according to Stahl, "reception theory, deconstructionism and performance theory." Her rendering calls attention to the rhetorically persuasive aspects of any oral tale, even one that claims to be based on personal experience, and makes reader response an essential part of analysis. These emphases seem salient not only for folklorists, but for critics and storytellers in the field of children's literature. (And it behooves us to remember that for many children, even in a television culture, personal narrative is their first introduction to narrative, as both listeners and tellers.)

The attractiveness of the book for me lay in Stahl's readable delineation of traditional, generally structuralist, analyses of folklore and of the ways in which poststructural theories could be made to work with them in the study of a rather neglected area of oral presentation: "a teller's own first-person, single-episodic account of a secular experience"; one which is not a "topical, one-time narrative" but a "personal experience" story that comes to be a "stable, repeated" narrative "in the teller's repertoire" (23).

The complexity of Stahl's application of theory to two short texts first demanded three chapters of thoughtful exposition. Such theoretical exposition did not make this reader, at least, impatient because it provided needed background and was enlivened by brief examples of other personal narratives. Moreover, I am already a convert to the contextualization of the literary experience that such theories provide. Chapters Four and Five give "tutor texts" of two personal narratives—"Koo-Nar, King of the Rats" told by Larry Schreiber, a friend of Stahl's sister, in *The Do Drop Inn*, a bar in Huntington, Indiana, "across the Wabash tracks on South Jefferson Street" (51), and "The Canary, or The Yellow Dress," told by Loretta Dolby, Stahl's mother, in the kitchen of the family home, also in Huntington. These tutor texts frequently interrupt the central narrative with clearly marked comments on not only the formal and substantive aspects of narratives themselves, but the concrete setting and audience responses in a particular performance. (Texts of the uninterrupted narratives are available to the reader in the appendix).¹

These narratives were not of the variety that begins with the prominent disclaimer of prose fiction that "any resemblance to real persons, living or dead, is purely coincidental." Rather, Stahl maintains, they provide a special instance when the actual speaker and the "I" of the narration are to be understood as identical and the other characters are frequently well known to the audience. Yet, as sophisticated critics might expect, the equation of the teller of tale with the "I" cannot be automatic. Other characterizations are also